

DEVELOPMENT OF NANO CALCIUM CARBONATE - POLYPROPYLENE COMPOSITE FOR AUTOMOTIVE APPLICATION

M.Y. A. Fuad¹, H. Hanim,¹ R. Zarina¹, Z.A. Mohd. Ishak,² & H. Azman³

¹*Plastics Technology Group, Advanced Materials Centre, SIRIM Berhad, P.O. Box 7035, 40911 Shah Alam, Malaysia*

²*School of Materials and Mineral Resources Engineering, Engineering Campus, Universiti Sains Malaysia, Seri Ampangan, 14300 Nibong Tebal, Penang, Malaysia*

³*Faculty of Chemical & Natural Resources Engineering, Universiti Teknologi Malaysia, Skudai, Johor, Malaysia*

SUMMARY: The objective of the study is to develop an automotive bumper grade nanocomposite by modifying polypropylene (PP) with nano-sized precipitated calcium carbonate (NPCC) filler and polyethylene elastomer (POE). Ternary polypropylene/polyolefin elastomer (POE)/calcium carbonate nanocomposites were prepared via melt blending in a co-rotating twin screw compounder using maleated PP (PP-g-MA) as a coupling agent. The NPCC added has an average measured primary particle size of 50 nm while the POE used was an ethylene-octene copolymer. Two NPCC filler loadings of 10 and 15 weight % were studied while the POE contents were varied between 0-30 weight %. Phase structures of both etched and unetched fractured surfaces of the nanocomposites were observed using a scanning electron microscope (SEM). At both NPCC levels studied, the impact strength of the homopolymer PP increases dramatically with increasing POE content. The maximum impact enhancement achieved for the neat PP was 450 J/m obtained for the nanocomposite with 15 wt. % NPCC and 30 wt. % POE. SEM photomicrographs of the nanocomposites showed a three-phase morphology of the dispersed POE and the nano-sized filler particles in the continuous PP matrix, except for the nanocomposite with the highest impact properties which showed evidence of a better adhesion between the POE and the PP. To obtain PP-NPCC composite of the required grade, it was crucial that the filler loading and POE content need to be delicately balanced. These factors greatly affect the properties of interest viz., the tensile, impact and modulus values as specified in the automotive specification of the bumper grade material.

KEYWORDS: Nano Calcium Carbonate, Polypropylene Composite, maleated PP (PP-g-MA), polyethylene elastomer (POE), impact modification, bumper grade material.

INTRODUCTION

The use of modified polypropylene (PP)-based materials as automotive components are well known, particularly the application as the bumper material. It is the intention of the local automotive manufacturer to substitute the use of imported modified PP material with that locally compounded and developed. A major automotive polymer compounder and the supplier of nano-sized CaCO₃ have commissioned a local research institution to undertake the task of developing the bumper grade material complying to the automotive standard of the national car manufacturer.

For applications requiring excellent impact properties, such as bumpers, PP material normally has to be blended with an elastomer component such as ethylene-propylene diene terpolymer

(EPDM) or ethylene-propylene copolymer (EPR). Although blending PP with elastomer has been proven to be an efficient way of increasing its impact toughness, one drawback is the significant loss of both tensile strength and stiffness of the PP, which cannot be accepted for certain applications. To compensate these detrimental effects, rigid mineral fillers are often added into the blend to achieve an optimum balance of toughness and stiffness [1]. After talc, calcium carbonate (CaCO_3) is the most common mineral filler used for PP due to its availability in readily useable form and low cost.

In addition to its ability to enhance modulus, the use of CaCO_3 to improve the impact strength of PP has also been reported. Zuiderduin et al. [2] reported that adding 60 wt.% of stearic acid treated CaCO_3 particles of 0.7 μm diameter into a PP matrix increased the impact strength and the modulus significantly. Earlier, Thio et al. [3] conducted similar also achieved considerable improvement in impact improvement using the 0.7 μm diameter stearic acid coated CaCO_3 particles at 30 vol.% loading. Both Zuiderduin et al. and Y.S. Thio et al. used a twin screw extruder to prepare the composites.

With the recent commercialisation of nano-sized CaCO_3 , studies using these nanoparticles as potential impact modifier for PP have also been carried out. Chan et al. [4] successfully prepared PP/ CaCO_3 nanocomposites via melt mixing in a Haake mixer and reported an impact enhancement of about twice that of the neat PP. Zhang et al. [5] carried out further studies to improve the dispersion of CaCO_3 nanoparticles in the PP matrix by adding a nonionic modifier, polyoxyethylene nonyphenol (PN) into the nanocomposites prepared in a twin screw extruder.

Work on phase structure of ternary PP/Elastomer/ CaCO_3 composites have been carried out by Premphet et al. [6]. The elastomer used were ethylene-octene copolymer (EOR) and ethylene-vinyl acetate (EVA). Their studies concluded that composites containing non-polar EOR showed separate dispersion of the elastomer and filler particles, while the use of polar EVA elastomer resulted in composites with encapsulation structure.

In this study, the mechanical properties and structure of PP/ CaCO_3 nanocomposites modified with polyethylene elastomer (POE) and maleated PP (PP-g-MAH) as the coupling agent were investigated. The nano filler used was nano-sized precipitated calcium carbonate (NPCC) coated with stearic acid and has an average diameter 50 nm.

EXPERIMENTAL

Materials

The PP material used was Titanpro 6331 produced by Titan Polymers Malaysia Sdn. Bhd. The homopolymer PP has a density of 0.899 g/cm^3 and a melt flow rate of 14 g/10 minutes (2.16kg at 230°C). The stearic acid coated NPCC was kindly supplied by NanoMaterials Pty. Ltd. The POE used was an Engage[®] 8150 produced by Dupont Dow Elastomers using refined metallocene catalyst often referred to as single-site or constrained geometry catalysts. The PP-g-MAH added as coupling agent was Orevac CA 100 from Autofina.

Preparation of PP/POE/ CaCO_3 nanocomposites

The NPCC and PP-g-MAH were dried in a vacuum oven at 80°C for at least 2 hours and allowed to cool down to room temperature. The PP/POE/NPCC were compounded in a

Berstoff co-rotating twin-screw extruder (ZE-25) with barrel temperature profile ranging from 180°C near the hopper to 200°C at the die. The screw speed was kept at 150 r.p.m. PP, POE and PP-g-MAH pellets were mechanically mixed before being introduced into the hopper and the NPCC was added via a secondary feeder located where the PP has already melted. The amount of PP-g-MAH added was 10 wt. % while the NPCC loadings used were 10 and 15 wt. %. POE compositions were varied between 0-30 wt.%. The nanocomposites were compounded twice to ensure homogeneous mixing of all ingredients. The palletised nanocomposite extrudates were injection moulded into ISO multi-purpose test specimens in accordance to ISO 3167:2002 using an Arburg 75-tonne injection moulding machine at about 190 °C melt temperature and 30°C mould temperature.

Mechanical Properties of the nanocomposites

Tensile properties were tested using an Instron 5556 Universal Testing Machine in accordance to ISO-527-1 at a crosshead speed of 50 mm/minute. Flexural properties were also measured using the same machine in accordance to ISO 178 at a crosshead speed of 2 mm/minute. The notched Izod impact strength was determined using a CEAST Resil Impactor according to ISO 180. All test specimens were condition in accordance to ISO 291 at 25±2°C and 55±5% Relative Humidity for at least 40 hours before being tested.

Phase Morphology

The morphology of the nanocomposites was examined using a Hitachi S-2500 Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM). Both etched and unetched impact fractured specimens were examined. Etching was carried using n-heptane at 50°C for 5 minutes to extract the elastomeric POE phase. Specimens were coated with gold prior to examination under the electron beam. An operating voltage of 10 kV and a magnification of 5,000 were used.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Mechanical Properties of the nanocomposites

The variation in mechanical properties with nanocomposite composition is detailed in Table 1. Results show that without any addition of POE, inclusion of up to 15 wt.% of the NPCC filler alone only improves the impact strength up to 1.5 times that of the neat PP. The NPCC also increased the stiffness of PP by about 30 %, and at the same time reducing the tensile strength by 10%. The increment in impact strength is not as significant when compared to the reported work done by Chan et al.[4]. This may possibly be attributed to inefficient mixing using the continuous twin screw compounder, which does not allow sufficient time for the nano-sized filler to be uniformly dispersed within the PP matrix as compared to the internal mixer used by other workers. The choice of the pilot plant scale compounder was made due to the initial intention of simulating the commercial continuous production in a typical material compounding plant. Nevertheless, the existing compounder, primarily designed for micro scale filler does not appear to have sufficient L/D ratio and high speed motor for efficient nano filler compounding.

At both 10 and 15 wt.% NPCC levels studied, the impact strength of the neat PP increases dramatically with increasing POE content. Addition of 15 wt. % NPCC to a PP modified with 30 wt. % POE increased the impact strength of PP from 18 J/m to 450 J/m. Without the NPCC filler, the enhanced the impact strength (due to POE alone) is only 330 J/m. When comparing the compositions with the same POE content, the nanocomposite with higher NPCC loading of 15 wt. % showed better impact enhancement as compared to the

nanocomposite loaded with 10 wt % NPCC (Figure 1). Thus, although the main contributor to the impact enhancement in PP appears to be from the POE, addition of NPCC further improved the impact strength by another 40% and thus surpassing the minimum requirement of the impact strength (390 J/m) in the bumper grade material specification.

As expected with addition of the POE, the modulus and tensile strength of PP are compromised inversely proportional with the POE loading. The main challenge in this study is to achieve the optimum formulation for bumper grade material, by balancing the need of high impact strength while maintaining respected values for stiffness and tensile properties. It appears that the formulation of sample PP-15-20 (15% NPCC, 20% POE) is the closest to complying with the automotive material specification.

Table 1. Mechanical Properties of PP/NPCC/POE nanocomposites

Sample number	Tensile Strength (MPa)	Elongation at Break (%)	Flexural Modulus (MPa)	Notched Izod Impact Strength (J/m)
PP	34.6	440	1,280	18
PP-10-0	33.3	220	1,580	28
PP-15-0	31.3	400	1,640	28
PP-10-10	28.7	120	1,310	44
PP-10-15	26.1	160	1,170	53
PP-10-20	24.7	180	1,160	78
PP-10-30	20.0	350	940	360
PP-15-15	26.1	280	1,100	65
PP-15-20	18.5	480	840	425
PP-15-30	18.2	480	770	450
PP-0-30	20.1	590	860	330
Commercial bumper material (Talc Filled PP)	18	> 400	1,370	245
MMC Specification: Modified PP for Exterior Parts	14.7 min.	150 min.	981 min.	390

Figure 1. The effect of composition on notched Izod impact strength at room temperature (25°C) of PP/POE/NPCC Nanocomposites

Several frameworks and models have been proposed to explain the toughening effect of rigid particulate filler such as CaCO_3 on semi-crystalline polymer such as PP. It was reported that in order for rigid filler particles to act as tougheners, they must fulfill certain requirements, among which include:

- the particles should be of small size (less than $5 \mu\text{m}$), otherwise the voids that are created would act as initiation sites for the fracture process
- the aspect ratio must be close to unity to avoid high stress concentrations
- the particle must debond prior to the yield strain of the matrix polymer in order to change the stress state of the matrix material
- the particles must be dispersed homogeneously in the matrix polymer and aggregation should be avoided[2]

Figure 2. TEM micrograph of the NPCC used in this study

The NPCC used in this study had a measured average primary particle size of 50 nm (0.05 μm), as shown in Figure 2. CaCO_3 filler is known to have a spherical shape with an aspect ratio of close to one. To study the dispersion of the NPCC in the matrix polymer, SEM photomicrographs of selected nanocomposites prepared in this study are shown in Figures 3 to 6.

Phase Morphology of the nanocomposites

Both etched and unetched impact fractured surfaces were investigated in this study. The aim of the etching process using n-heptane was to dissolve the POE phase without affecting the PP phase and the NPCC filler present. The SEM photomicrograph in Figure 3(b) of etched PP filled with 10 wt. % NPCC without any POE, shows evidence that the n-heptane did not disturb the NPCC, as the filler can still be observed in the PP matrix after undergoing the etching process.

From Figures 3 (a) and (b), it can be seen that, without the presence of any POE, the distribution of the NPCC in the PP matrix is quite homogeneous. However, the dispersion of the NPCC is observed to be rather poor, as the size of the NPCC in this photomicrograph is measured to be between 0.125 – 0.25 μm . This indicates that agglomeration of the nano-sized CaCO_3 has occurred during compounding, and may have resulted in the modest increment of impact strength observed for this compound.

(a)

(b)

Figure 3. SEM photomicrographs of unetched (a) and etched (b) impact fractured surface of PP-10-0

It may be observed from Figures 4 and 5 that the POE is dispersed as a separate phase structure within the continuous PP matrix. The etched surfaces reveal small spherical domains where the POE has been removed, and the number of these domains increased with increasing POE content. The average size of the domains, however, decreases with increasing POE content. The smallest average size of the POE domain for the compositions with high impact strength was found to be about 0.6 μm . This diameter size is in the reported range required to toughen blends where the matrix polymer is ductile [7].

(a)

(b)

Figure 4. SEM photomicrographs of unetched (a) and etched (b) impact fractured surface of PP-10-20

(a)

(b)

Figure 5. SEM photomicrographs of unetched (a) and etched (b) impact fractured surface of PP-10-30

In the unetched SEM photomicrograph of the nanocomposite which displayed one of the highest impact strength (Figure 6), the separate POE droplets, previously observed in other compositions, was not found to be so apparent. This better adhesion between the PP matrix and the POE may possibly have caused the dramatic improvement observed in the impact strength for this composition.

Figure 6. SEM photomicrographs of unetched (a) and etched (b) impact fractured surface of PP-15-20

CONCLUSION

Addition of NPCC and POE have resulted in a significant improvement in the mechanical properties of interest of the ternary PP/POE/CaCO₃ nanocomposites. The impact properties have been greatly improved though at the expense of the tensile and flexural properties. The objective to achieve a bumper grade formulation is almost achieved, albeit a small deficiency in the flexural modulus. In due time, it is believed this may be achieved through addition of a proprietary additive to tailor made the end properties as are required in the automotive specification.

REFERENCES

- [1] B. Pukanszky, Polypropylene: Structure, blends and composites, 1995, Chapman & Hall
- [2] W.C.J. Zuiderduin, C. Westzaan, J.Huetink, R.J. Gaymans Polymer 2003; 44: 261-275
- [3] Y.S. Thio, A.S. Argon, R.E. Cohen, M. Weinberg Polymer 2002; 43: 3661-3674
- [4] Chi-Ming Chan, Jingshen Wu, Jian-Xiong Li, Ying-Kit Cheung Polymer 2002; 43: 2981-2992
- [5] Qing-Xin Zhang, Zhong-Zhen Yu, Xiao-Lin Xie, Yiu-Wing Mai Polymer 2004; 45: 5985-5994
- [6] K. Premphet, P. Horanont Polymer 2000; 41: 9283-9290
- [7] T. McNally, P. McShane, G.M. Nally, W.R. Murphy, M. Cook, A. Miller Polymer 2002; 43: 3785-3793

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